

CULTURAL NAVIGATION TOOLKIT

for Social Workers

From Research to Practice

PURPOSE

This toolkit translates research evidence into practical guidance for frontline social workers to navigate the cultural contexts of service users.

HOW TO USE IT

Use the Quick Self-Check

- If 2+ items are 'No', select one tool based on the area where you find cultural differences most challenging to navigate.
- Apply only the tool(s) relevant to your case. There is no expectation to use all tools in a single case.

QUICK SELF-CHECK - PAUSE BEFORE YOU ACT

Please respond with Y or N (yes or no) in the box provided

- Am I being curious rather than making assumptions?
- Understood the difference between cultural practice and risk of welfare?
- Looked for a cultural broker/ISW colleague to consult?
- Tried community/family solutions before escalating?

If you ticked "No" twice or more - select a tool below

Tool 1: Outsider Inquisitiveness

The 3 Curious Questions

Use When: You don't understand the family's perspective or feel stuck in assumptions

- 1 How is this usually handled in your family and community?
- 2 What feels hardest right now, and what would help me understand your experience better?
- 3 What would feel respectful to you in how services work with your family?

Tool 2: Navigating Culture and Safeguarding Risk

Use When: The line between cultural practice and safeguarding concerns feels unclear

Column A: Cultural practice/Belief	Column B: Risk to Welfare
 Describe the belief/tradition Example: In Child X's case, some family members view disability as shameful	 Describe evidence of harm Example: In Child X's case, the child was slapped, which raised safeguarding concerns

Cultural beliefs or practices do not justify harm. Safeguarding duties still apply

Tool 3: Cultural Meta-Perspectives

Use When: Cultural norms and safeguarding standards appear to conflict

UK services have a legal duty to ensure the person's safety and meet their needs. We also understand there may be family expectations or beliefs.

How can we work together to meet your needs while respecting your family's views?

Tool 4: A Three-Tier Support Map For Culturally-Informed Solutions

Tier 1: Family & Community

Who in the family, community, faith group and community can support now?

Tier 2: Voluntary

Local charities, culture-specific organisations, care groups

Tier 3: Statutory

Direct Payment, Commissioned care, Short breaks

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Tool 5: Cultural Reflection with International Social Workers

Use in Team Meetings and Supervision

- 1 Pair a UK social worker and an internationally experienced social worker
- 2 Share a case where cultural understanding improved practice or outcomes.
- 3 Share one practical skill that helped you navigate cultural differences in that case.
- 4 The team identifies three culturally grounded skills to trial and reflect upon in practice next month

ALIGNMENT WITH PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS

Social Work
England Standards
3, 4, 5

PCF
Diversity & Equality,
Critical Reflection

KSS
Working with
complexity, risk,
and diversity.

